

Social cognition in degenerative cerebellar ataxias

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Social cognition (SC) refers to a set of skills necessary for successful social communication and interpersonal relationships. Accumulating evidence points toward a crucial role of the cerebellum in SC. This narrative review summarizes and discusses the social cognitive impairment in cerebellar ataxias (CA), a group of hereditary neurodegenerative diseases of the cerebellum. Substantial impairment in emotion recognition and theory of mind, two essential components of SC, is present in CA. The social cognitive impairment is largely independent of the motor disability, general cognitive deficit, or neuropsychiatric symptoms. Since the impairment reaches comparable levels to autism or schizophrenia, it can substantially impact patients' quality of life and deserves further attention in future research.

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Introduction

Social cognition (SC) is a cognitive domain comprising a complex set of abilities for processing social information. These skills are necessary for understanding other people's emotions and thoughts and responding adequately to them. Therefore, SC is crucial for successful communication, social interactions, and, consequently, for well-being [1].

The two most researched core components of SC are emotion recognition (ER) and theory of mind (ToM) [2]. ER refers to the ability to discern emotions from verbal or nonverbal cues such as facial expression, eye contact, body posture, or prosody. ToM, or 'mentalizing,' is the capacity to comprehend other people's mental states and understand that they can differ from one's own. ToM can be further subdivided into affective ToM (understanding others' emotions) and cognitive ToM (understanding intentions or beliefs) [3].

Social cognitive impairment is a core component of several neurodevelopmental (e.g. autism), psychiatric (e.g. schizophrenia, bipolar disorder), and neurodegenerative (e.g. frontotemporal lobar degeneration) disorders and contributes to worse everyday functioning in these disorders [2,4,5].

Impairment in SC, involving both ER and ToM, has also been demonstrated in cerebellar disorders [6,7]. It constitutes a part of the cerebellar cognitive affective syndrome (CCAS), a distinctive set of nonmotor cerebellar symptoms [8,9].

One of the specific mechanisms by which the cerebellum exerts its social role is proposed in the sequencing hypothesis [7,10]. According to this hypothesis, the cerebellum detects and analyzes temporal and spatial sequences in both sensorimotor and higher-order cognitive processes and uses the sequences to create internal models as a basis for outcome prediction. The cerebellum then compares the predicted outcomes with the actual situation. In case of a discrepancy, it employs its modulatory effect on relevant cortical regions to adjust the outcome. Specific cerebellar regions have recently been linked to social sequencing [7].

Even though SC is a dissociable cognitive domain, its impairment in other diseases may be influenced by a coexisting general neurocognitive deficit [2]. In some disorders, the relation between SC and neuropsychiatric symptoms, such as depression and anxiety, has also been demonstrated [2,11]. In cerebellar diseases, these links were not systematically explored. However, specific parts of the cerebellum (particularly Crus I–II of the posterior lobe), which are linked to SC, can be distinguished from other parts of the nonmotor cerebellum involved in cognitive processing and affective regulation

[7,12]. This fact suggests a possible dissociation between SC and cognitive/neuropsychiatric functions in cerebellar patients.

Cerebellar ataxias (CA) are a clinically and genetically diverse group of neurodegenerative diseases characterized by predominant impairment of the cerebellum and its connections. To a varying degree, they also affect other structures of the nervous system, such as the basal ganglia, brainstem, and spinal cord. The most common types of CA are the autosomal-dominant spinocerebellar ataxias (SCA) and autosomal-recessive Friedreich ataxia (FRDA). While the main clinical hallmark of these disorders is progressive gait and limb incoordination and other motor symptoms, CCAS is also frequently present. It is characterized by the presence of cognitive dysfunction and neuropsychiatric symptoms and considerably influences the clinical picture and quality of life (QoL) [13–15]. CCAS is particularly prevalent in SCA2, 3, and 17 [16]. Its presence has also been demonstrated in FRDA [17].

The goal of this narrative review is to

- 1) Summarize the impairment of SC (ER and ToM) in degenerative CA and the differences between particular CA subtypes.
- 2) Identify possible associations between social cognitive impairment and the severity of ataxia, global or specific cognitive deficit, or the severity of the neuropsychiatric symptoms.
- 3) Examine the degree to which social cognitive impairment identified in formal testing reflects real-life problems in everyday functioning and the QoL of individuals with CA.

Methods

Studies concerning SC in degenerative CA were retrieved from PubMed and Web of Science using a combination of the following keywords: ‘spinocerebellar ataxia’ or ‘Friedreich ataxia’ and ‘social cognition,’ ‘theory of mind,’ or ‘emotion recognition.’ We included studies published in English from 2000 to April 2023, with particular attention to studies published in the last two years. Since SC in CA is a relatively new field, it was, however not necessary to exclude any relevant article due to these criteria. We included only studies on patients comprising genetically confirmed diagnoses of SCA or FRDA. We identified 18 papers related to social cognitive impairment in CA. Two focused only on ER, one on ER and ToM, and the rest studied only ToM. The results are summarized in [Table 1](#).

Impairment of social cognition in cerebellar ataxias

Existing studies used tests of ER or ToM developed and utilized in noncerebellar disorders (for details on individual articles and their methodology see [Table 1](#)).

Regarding ER, two of the three existing studies found significant impairment in ER in SCA and FRDA patients. The study on SCA noted that patients were more affected in recognizing complex social emotions compared with basic emotions [18]. Similarly, the study on FRDA found impairment in the Geneva Emotion Recognition Test (GERT), a complex task requiring the recognition of 14 different emotions [19]. In contrast, another study on FRDA patients did not confirm a significant impairment of ER but only tested basic emotions and compared the results with mean scores in the general population instead of a matched control group [20]. It has been hypothesized that while basic emotions are innate and universal, social emotions are learned during one’s lifetime. This process may be disrupted by cerebellar degeneration [18].

Most studies tested ToM and generally agree that there is a significant impairment compared with healthy individuals in both cognitive and affective ToM [21–33].

Conflicting results across several studies come from the Emotion Attribution Test (EA), which requires a participant to determine how a character in a short story feels. Several studies found no significant impairment in CA patients, while others report only selective impairment for certain emotions or SCA subtypes [21,25,27,28,33,34]. Studies using the EA Test along with several complex story-based tests tapping into both affective and cognitive ToM (e.g. Faux Pas Test, Happe’s Strange Stories Test) consistently found a dissociation between preserved EA and impaired complex ToM, suggesting that cerebellar processing is particularly important in complex tasks requiring multiple steps and a high level of prediction [21,25,33].

Considering the sequencing hypothesis of cerebellar functioning, one innovative study employed a series of specific cognitive tests targeting social action sequences. In line with the hypothesis, patients were indeed most impaired in reconstructing the chronological order of social events, while less impaired in mentalizing tasks that did not include a clear sequencing element [35].

There are no apparent differences in SC between particular subtypes of SCA or between SCA and FRDA. However, a low number of participants in the existing studies and the fact that many of them evaluated mixed cohorts of patients without distinguishing the subtypes limit the possibility to draw conclusions in this regard [23,25,29,30].

Relation of social cognition with the severity of ataxia, cognition, and neuropsychiatric symptoms

The ataxia severity is traditionally evaluated mainly by the presence and gravity of ataxic motor symptoms such

Table 1
Summary of studies on social cognitive impairment in CA.

Title	Patients	Methods	Results	Correlation with cognition	Correlation with NPS	Correlation with ataxia
<i>Studies on ER</i> D'Agata et al., 2011 [18]	SCA2 (n = 9), SCA6 (n = 5), SCA7 (n = 2), SCA8 (n = 4)	Ekman 60 faces, Tamietto 50 faces	Significantly worse results in patients in both tasks, patients were above the cutoff in Ekman task, under cutoff in Tamietto task	+	0	0
Costabile et al., 2018 [19]	FRDA (n = 20)	GERT	Impairment in GERT, worst scores in recognizing amusement, sadness, interest, and pleasure	+	+	0
<i>Studies on both ER and ToM</i> Sayah et al., 2017 [20]	FRDA (n = 47)	Ekman 35 faces, FPT	No impairment	NA	NA	NA
<i>Studies on ToM</i> Garrard et al., 2008 [21]	SCA3 (n = 6), SCA6 (n = 9)	EA, HSS, and social situations	Impairment in HSS, no impairment in EA, and social situations	0	NA	NA
Sokolovskiy et al., 2010 [34]	SCA1 (n = 2), SCA2 (n = 3), SCA7 (n = 2)	EA, HSS	EA: impairment in SCA2, selective impairment in certain emotions in SCA7, and no impairment in SCA1 HSS: impaired in one SCA1 patient, normal in SCA2 and SCA7	NA	NA	NA
Moriarty et al., 2016 [22]	SCA1 (n = 2), SCA2 (n = 2), SCA3 (n = 2), SCA6 (n = 4), SCA7 (n = 3)	HSS	SCA1, SCA2, and SCA7 were just above the threshold of impairment at baseline; at follow-up (mean 7.5 years), all groups scored below the threshold, SCA7 demonstrated the smallest decrease in score over time	NA	NA	NA
Hoche et al., 2016 [23]	31 patients with complexocerebellar degeneration (SCA1, SCA2, SCA3, SCA7, SCA17, AOA2, MSA-C, FRDA, complex cerebellar degeneration of unknown etiology, and left cerebellar injury with brainstem involvement), 26 patients with disease confined to the cerebellum (isolated cerebellar hypoplasia, SCA6, SCA8, ILOCA, ARCA-1, EA-2, and isolated cerebellar injury) FRDA (n = 22)	RMET	Impairment in RMET	NA	0	NA
Dogan et al., 2016 [24]		FPT	Impairment, especially in the appraisal of intentions and empathy, no significant differences in neutral stories or control questions	NA	NA	NA
Van Overwalle, 2019 [35]	11 patients with a primary neurodegenerative ataxia (including SCA8, SCA14, and ILOCA) or cerebellar injury	Picture sequencing task, trait attribution, causal attribution, and Dewey social stories	Impairment on picture sequencing task and trait attribution, no impairment on causal attribution and social stories	NA	NA	+
Clausi et al., 2019 [25]	SCA1 (n = 2), SCA2 (n = 11), SCA15 (n = 2), SCA28 (n = 1), FRDA (n = 2), ILOCA (n = 8), Cerebellitis (n = 1)	EA, FPT, HSS, and RMET	Impairment in RMET and HSS, no impairment in EA FPT: selective impairment in the 'faux	0	+	0

Table 1 (continued)

Title	Patients	Methods	Results	Correlation with cognition	Correlation with NPS	Correlation with ataxia
Lupo et al., 2020 [28]	SPG7 (n = 6)	EA, HSS, and RMET	pas' stories, no impairment in the 'no-faux pas' stories Impairment in RMET and HSS EA: selective impairment for embarrassment	NA	NA	NA
Tamaš et al., 2021 [29]	SCA1 (n = 12), SCA2 (n = 6), ILOCA (n = 16)	FPT, RMET	RMET: impaired in all patient groups FPT: impaired in all patient groups, lower scores in SCA1 and SCA2 than ILOCA	+	+	+
Clausi et al., 2021a [27]	SCA2 (n = 13)	EA, FPT, and RMET	Impairment in RMET and FPT EA: not impaired in total score, impaired in stories featuring anger	0	0	0
Clausi et al., 2021b [26]	21 adults with ASD, 36 patients with degenerative cerebellar damage (SCA1, 2, 6, 15, 28, SPG7, FRDA, ICA, and cerebellitis)	FPT, RMET	Impairment in RMET and FPT in cerebellar and ASD patients, no significant difference between the cerebellar and ASD groups	NA	0	0
García et al., 2022 [30]	n = 38 (ADCA=34.2%, ARCA=44.8%, X-linked =10.5%, mitochondrial=2.6%, and sporadic=7.9%) SCA1 (n = 16)	HSS	Impaired in patients, no differences between patient groups	NA	NA	0
Contaldi et al., 2022 [31]	SCA1 (n = 16)	EA	Impaired, mostly in fear and anger	NA	NA	0
Elyoseph et al., 2023 [32]	SCA3 (18 symptomatic, 5 presymptomatic)	FB, RMET, and TAS-20	Impairment in FB and RMET, higher scores in TAS-20	NA	NA	0
Olivito et al., 2023 [33]	32 patients with cerebellar neurodegeneration, 21 adults with ASD, and 13 patients with BD-2	EA, FPT, and RMET	EA: ASD group had significantly lower scores than controls, no significant differences in other pairwise comparisons between groups FPT and RMET: all three clinical groups had significantly lower scores than controls, no significant differences among the clinical groups	NA	NA	NA

Abbreviations: ASD autism spectrum disorder; BD-2 bipolar disorder type 2; EA Emotion Attribution Test; FB False Belief Test; FPT Faux Pas Test; GERT Geneva Emotion Recognition Test; HSS Happé's Strange Stories; NPS neuropsychiatric symptoms; RMET Reading the Mind in the Eyes Test; TAS-20 Toronto Alexithymia Scale
Note: ER tests: Ekman and Tarnieto faces, GERT; ToM tests: EA, FB, FPT, HSS, and RMET

as gait and limb incoordination, dysarthria, or oculomotor disorders. The commonly used measures are the Scale for the Assessment and Rating of Ataxia (SARA) and the International Cooperative Ataxia Rating Scale (ICARS). These scales are also well-correlated with measures of activities of daily living [36,37].

The relationship between SC and the severity of ataxia was probed in ten studies. The majority of studies (8/10) found no correlation between either ER or ToM and ataxia severity [18,19,25–27,30–32]. This is analogous to the situation with ataxia scales and neuropsychiatric symptoms [38]. Similar, albeit less consistent, are the results of studies correlating ataxia scales with cognition [39]. In total, the results suggest that motor and non-motor symptoms of CA are likely dissociated.

Several studies examined the possible relationship between SC and other cognitive domains, mainly executive functions, but also language, memory, and visuospatial functions. There seems to be a dissociation between ToM, which was found to be relatively independent of the neurocognitive impairment, and ER, which was related to general cognition and other cognitive domains [18,19,21,25,27,40].

ER, tested by GERT in FRDA patients, was notably linked to a visuospatial memory and learning test (Spatial Recall Test) [19]. As the authors of the study point out, reduced visuospatial learning can lead to the inability to perceive the face as a whole and instead focus on particular details. This phenomenon, the so-called ‘weak central coherence,’ has been described in individuals with autism spectrum disorders (ASD) and is used to explain their facial ER deficit [19,41]. A study examining the relationship between facial ER in SCA patients and verbal memory, attention, and semantic fluency, found that the results in these domains were correlated with the recognition of basic emotions [18].

Contrary to the finding of a close relationship between ToM and executive functions in patients with non-cerebellar pathology, several studies in patients with CA confirmed that executive functions do not correlate with patients’ results in tests of either affective or cognitive ToM [21,25,27,40]. One exception is a study which noticed that the Stroop Color and Word Test predicted the performance on the Reading the Mind in the Eyes Test (RMET) in patients with SCA1 and SCA2 but not in patients with the idiopathic late-onset cerebellar ataxia (ILOCA) [29]. The same study found a correlation between the ToM tests and a measure of language functions. The authors conclude that language is an inherently human instrument for social communication, and SC largely depends on intact language abilities. This could be the reason why diminished semantic ability can cause difficulties in verbal attribution of emotions and

comprehending social situations [29]. These intriguing findings await confirmation by other studies.

Another interesting question is the relationship between social cognitive deficits and neuropsychiatric symptoms such as depression and anxiety, commonly reported in CA [38]. In noncerebellar patients, depression and anxiety generally have a negative impact on ER and ToM [42–45]. Concerning cerebellar research, the data from anatomical and functional neuroimaging studies show that neuropsychiatric symptoms result from the disruption of pathways between the vermis and the limbic system, while SC impairment is the result of lesions in areas of the posterolateral cerebellar hemispheres connected to the default mode network [46]. This could be the reason why most studies on ataxia patients found no correlation between SC and affective symptoms [18,23,25–27]. One exception was a study that reported worsened recognition of pride and irritation in patients with higher trait anxiety [19]. Another found a correlation between anxiety and depression scores and performance on RMET in ILOCA but not SCA patients [29]. It should be noted that the relation to other neuropsychiatric symptoms than depression and anxiety was not examined yet and could be the aim of future studies.

Impact of social cognitive impairment on everyday life in cerebellar ataxias

Everyday functioning and health-related quality of life (QoL) are commonly impaired in individuals with CA [15,47–49]. According to one study, ataxia severity, nonataxia neurological symptoms, and depression together explained only 30% of QoL variability in SCA; searching for other factors is therefore necessary [14]. In a recent work, several items compromising the QoL that do not relate to motor impairment have been endorsed by patients with CA and their caregivers [15]. The impact of SC impairment on QoL in CA has not yet been examined, but evidence from other disorders highlights its importance. In schizophrenia, SC better explained functional outcomes compared with neurocognition [5], and in ASD, SC impairment contributed to worse social functioning [50,51]. Studies directly comparing SC between CA and ASD and bipolar disorder found a similar level of impairment [26,33]. Additional support may be drawn from comparing studies examining SC in CA with analogous studies on schizophrenia or ASD. CA patients scored similarly to schizophrenia patients in RMET (scores 22.8/36 in schizophrenia vs. 21.5/36 in CA) [29,52] or to individuals with ASD in Strange Stories Test (scores 11.6/16 in ASD vs. 10.9/16 in CA) [30,53].

Regarding subjectively perceived QoL in schizophrenia and ASD, the impact of SC impairment was moderated

by other factors, such as insight [54,55]. However, since insight is not usually impaired in CA, SC could be explored as a direct contributing factor.

Although these areas are exciting to explore, we acknowledge several challenges associated with the measurements. Many traditional SC measures have been criticized for their limited ecological validity [56]. Virtual reality-based tasks could overcome this issue once their clinical utility for CA patients is established [57]. Another way to improve the measurement validity of SC in CA could be to focus on processes specifically impaired in cerebellar patients. In this context, using tasks assessing social sequencing should be particularly promising [58]. Ataxia-specific and ecologically valid methods are also needed to assess QoL and everyday functioning accurately. Despite these challenges, clarifying the links between SC impairment and functional outcomes and QoL in CA deserves proper attention for its potential to improve intervention strategies.

Conclusion and future directions

Current research confirms an impairment of SC (both in ER and ToM) in CA, integrating SC in the spectrum of its nonmotor manifestation. However, there is limited data to determine its prevalence in different CA subtypes.

Social cognitive impairment in CA is mostly dissociated from ataxia severity, general cognition, and neuropsychiatric symptoms and its physiological underpinnings differ from those causing motor, cognitive, and neuropsychiatric symptoms. One exception is ER, which was associated with several cognitive domains.

Comparison with studies in noncerebellar patients reveals that the level of SC impairment can be as severe as in schizophrenia or ASD and thus can considerably influence the QoL in CA. Implementing SC assessment into the standard diagnostic work-up in CA patients would bring more information about this separate cognitive domain, which is often neglected in clinical settings yet could directly impact the rehabilitations and focused support of these patients.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Simona Karamazovova: Conceptualization, Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, **Veronika Matuskova:** Conceptualization, Writing - Original Draft, **Natalie Svecova:** Investigation, Writing - Original Draft, **Martin Vyhnalek:** Conceptualization, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Declaration of Competing Interest

None.

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